

METHODS OF WORKING WITH LEXICAL MATERIAL AT THE INITIAL STAGE OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: Learning foreign languages is one of the important requirements of today. Language materials are the basis for learning a foreign language. This article analyzes the role of vocabulary and the usage of different innovative methods in teaching English.

Keywords: foreign languages, language material, vocabulary, innovative methods, stages of teaching vocabulary.

It is known that the basis of foreign language material is vocabulary. When teaching students a foreign language, it is very important to know the peculiarities of the vocabulary of this language, as well as the peculiarities of the native language and Russian words.

The introduction of CEFR into the education system of Uzbekistan requires language learners to have sufficient skills and competencies in all types of speech activity. To do this, you must have a vocabulary in the foreign language being studied.

It is impossible to teach and master the types of speech activity, that is, speaking, listening, reading and writing, without mastering the vocabulary perfectly. Vocabulary is used as material for speech activity. The language material is essential for any oral activity. If there is no language material, you will not work to speak a foreign language. You can understand the meaning of English speech based on the learned words by listening to it.

The lexical side of speech has its own characteristics. The student cannot speak without knowing the words. The lexical aspect of reading is also a particular problem. The reader, the student, sees and accepts in his research.

It is also necessary to work separately on the lexical side of the written expression of opinion. In order for a student to write meaningful and correct information through a lexicon, it is necessary to be able to write, pronounce and read a word. As can be seen from the above, vocabulary is necessary for all types of speech activity. For this reason, the role of vocabulary in the formation and development of students' oral speech is important.

Today, interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is growing day by day. Until now, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, while modern technologies teach them to search, independently study and analyze, and even draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, training and education of the individual and at the same time performs the function of management and leadership. In the learning process, the student becomes the main figure.

In the process of teaching a foreign language, learning new words is carried out in three stages. At the first stage, the introduction, the teacher introduces new words into the lesson using different techniques.

The correct organization of this process by the teacher largely affects the efficiency of work at the following stages. A foreign language teacher needs to provide detailed information about the pronunciation, meaning, form and place of a new word in a certain grammatical structure.

The choice of methods for teaching vocabulary also depends on the nature of the word being studied. If a word denotes a specific thing, an object, then the meaning of the word is conveyed to students by directly showing it. For example, you can teach by showing words such as *book, pen, pencil, desk, table, chair*.

It will also be very interesting for students if the teacher uses facial expressions and various actions to reveal the meaning of the word. At the initial stage of learning a foreign language, it is also effective to learn new words through various activities, games and colorful pictures. Because children at this stage (grades 1-4) willingly perform activities consisting of movements. The performance of songs and poems also greatly helps students of this age in learning a new foreign language. When using such methods, learning new words will help them stay in memory for a long time. Reflecting on the work on lexical material at the first stage, we want to dwell on what techniques and interactive techniques should be used.

"Brainstorming"

This method is aimed at activating students in the learning process. The teacher asks students to express their opinion on a particular topic or lexical material to be studied. The teacher does not criticize the opinions expressed, even if they are not related to the chosen topic. Through Brainstorming, he helps students develop their abilities such as free thinking and critical observation.

"Listen and Do"

When the teacher uses this method, he first explains to the students that they must repeat the words they hear through actions. Students listen carefully to what the teacher says and begin to do so. New words, the meaning of which is revealed by actions, are stored in memory for a long time.

"Mimic Story"

This method is used by the teacher to reveal the meaning of certain words with the help of facial expressions. The teacher reads a simple story, with the help of facial expressions conveys to the students the meaning of new words in the story. For example, words such as sad, happy, angry are explained to students using facial expressions.

We believe that the above methods will be appropriate if they are used to teach new words to students at the initial stage of learning a foreign language.

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